

SURFACE ENGINEERING ISSUES IN COMPOSITE CORE STRUCTURES (GRAPHITIC FOAM)

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ABSTRACT

The micro-cellular graphitic foam is a porous lightweight solid made of interconnected ligaments and cells of graphitic planes. Since the structure is 80-90% porous, these solids have a high interface/volume ratio, and surface driven properties such as atmospheric tolerance and bond formation with the matrix material are crucial for applicability. This calls for controlled surface modification, which is complicated by the fact that the “surface” is made of non-planar cell walls, most of which are accessible only through narrow pore openings. This has led us to investigate selected thin film modification techniques that can permeate the porous micro-cellular structure. The idea is to tailor surface-related properties (such as environmental stability, bonding & adhesion of suitable matrix material, surface flaw tolerance and wear resistance) without compromising the desirable bulk properties of graphite.

Several types of modification, using liquid-phase and plasma-phase treatments, have been discussed. One of the goals is to improve composite formation. If a composite is to be made with the foam, it needs to be infiltrated with a matrix phase (e.g. epoxy for structural composite or metal for thermal composite). Enhanced infiltration of the matrix material and optimum bond-strength is achieved by surface treatments that increase chemical affinity between the two phases. Hydrophilic coatings that increase oxygen-functional groups on the surface are seen to be very effective. The second modification goal is to enhance the foam’s durability as a stand-alone solid (such as in a lightweight sandwich structure or thermal dissipation foam). Coatings that incorporate moisture-repellent and chemically inert groups, which make the surface less susceptible to environmental degradation, achieve this. Several aspects of these coatings have been discussed including (a) Chemistry of specific surface functional groups. (b) Contact angle changes with water and (c) Infiltration of water, which is a predictor of infiltration of other polar compounds. The significance of these results to our understanding of composite interfaces and future composite fabrication have been discussed.

Keywords: Carbon, Composite core structures, Emerging manufacturing technologies, Interfacial bonding, Surface Engineering.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The micro-cellular graphitic foam^{1 2 3 4 5 6} is a new and exciting structure that is a porous and lightweight solid made of crystallized sp^2 carbon [Figure 1]. Unlike the cylindrical graphite fibers of today, this solid is completely isotropic, which makes it a promising candidate for near-net shape fabrication of structural and thermal-management composites. It would offer the advantages of graphite (high strength and high thermal conductivity parallel to the basal plane) without the disadvantages of anisotropy and fiber-lay up requirements.

Figure 1: Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of typical graphitic foam.

However, due to the extremely high surface/volume ratio of this structure, a basic understanding and control of the surfaces of these solids is essential⁷. Sufficient infiltration of the matrix material (epoxy or other resins) and optimum bonding between these phases is crucial for proper functioning of any composite structure. Even in applications where stand-alone graphitic foam may be preferable (such as lightweight sandwich structures or thermal dissipation materials), coating of the surface for corrosion/degradation resistance would be important. Whereas several investigators have focused on surface properties of cylindrical fibers, small particles, and whiskers of carbon,^{8 9 10 11 12 13 14} very little is understood about the surface of micro-cellular graphitic foam. This is further complicated by the fact that the surfaces of these structures will include edge atoms as well as planar atoms in various geometrical arrangements, as shown in the close-up microstructure of Figure 2.

The aim of this project is to understand possible modification techniques of the foam surface in light of what is known about other types of carbon. Two types of surface

modification outcomes have been attempted: (i) Modifications to make the surface more reactive so that infiltration of composite core materials (such as epoxy) will be enhanced, and (ii) Modifications to make the surface more inert so that when the foam is used in stand-alone structures, it will not be degraded by atmospheric moisture, pollutants etc.

Figure 2: Close-up view of Ligaments (notice stacked planes, irregular flakes, beams and fibers)

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Graphitized foam prepared from Mitsubishi synthetic pitch using the AFRL patented technique⁵ has been used in this study. Foam fabrication involves placing a puck of pitch in a pressure vessel and introducing inert gas at controlled temperature and pressure until the bubbles create a foam of desired porosity. Subsequent heat treatments in controlled atmospheres convert the pitch foam to carbon and then to graphite.

In addition to foam, flat graphite surfaces were used for XPS quantification. These planar surfaces were obtained by cleaving single crystal graphite prepared by Structure Probe Inc.

The surface treatments studied are listed below. The first two treatments involve plasma-assisted deposition and the third one involves simple liquid phase modification. The first plasma treatment is designed to make the foam surface more reactive and the second one is designed to make it passive. In general, oxygen-containing functional groups on the surface enhance reactivity and water-affinity or “hydrophilic” behavior. Such surfaces also tend to have higher infiltration of polar fluids such as epoxy resins, and of metallic species. On the other hand, the second treatment is designed to make the surface “hydrophobic” or water repellent, which in turn discourages infiltration of most contaminants. This can be done by adding fluorocarbon groups to the surface. The third (liquid phase approach) is designed to test if an in-expensive one-step method that is often successful in large scale carbon fiber applications can provide some surface reactivity enhancement in micro-cellular graphitic foams. The treatments are outlined below:

- a) Plasma enhanced coating of an ultra-thin reactive film (silica-like layer): This was done using a mixture of HMDSO (hexa-methyl di-siloxane) and Argon in a commercial microwave plasma reactor (V15GL manufactured by PlasmaTech Inc.) at 250 W power, 60Pa pressure and ambient temperature.
- b) Plasma enhanced coating of an inert film (teflon-like layer): This was performed in the same chamber as above, using simple fluoro-carbon monomers (CF_4 and/or C_3F_8) in the plasma.
- c) Exposure to an oxidizing chemical such as Nitric Acid: Foam samples were immersed in aqueous Nitric acid (HNO_3) solutions for specific times and subsequent changes monitored. This approach was earlier shown to be effective in increasing surface reactivity of some cylindrical carbon fibers⁸ but its applicability to a micro-cellular surface has not been investigated to the best of our knowledge.

X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed in a Kratos - Axis Ultra System using monochromatized Al $K\alpha$ photons.

Contact angle changes on plasma-modified surfaces were recorded in a standard Video Contact Angle (VCA) monitor. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was performed on fractured surfaces of carbon foam using a JEOL 35 Scanning Electron Microscope with 8 nm resolution.

Water absorption in foam was measured by weighing rectangular pieces of foam on a micro-balance, and then immersing them in distilled water for a specific time. Subsequently, the soaked pieces were placed on absorbent paper for five minutes (to catch the dripping water) and their weights measured again. The percentage change in weight provided a quantitative measure of how much water infiltrates into the foam.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The influence of two plasma coatings on wettability (contact angle with water) is shown in Figure 3. It can be clearly seen that the foam treated with HMDSO containing plasma (method a) soaks up water rapidly and that treated with Fluorocarbon-containing plasma (method b) becomes hydrophobic. Compared to untreated foam that has a contact angle of about 77 degrees, HMDSO-treated foam has a contact angle of 0 and fluorocarbon-treated foam has a contact angle higher than 140 degrees, same as that of commercial Teflon.

The functionality of surface groups were carefully monitored using X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). XPS data is extremely useful in this regard because, not only does it identify what elements are present at the top 1-5 nm of the surface, but it also distinguishes different chemical bonding states of the identified atom. . In order to be able to perform quantitative chemical analyses of the outer atomic layers without concerns about surface roughness, high resolution XPS spectra were also taken on identically created coatings on atomically flat single crystal graphite crystals. For acid treated surfaces (as in method c), the only change observed was an increase in surface

oxygen content as shown in Figure 4. As shown later by water uptake measurements, this small change can cause significant changes in surface reactivity and infiltration of polar fluids.

Figure 3: Contact angle of water on graphitic foams (i) untreated (ii) plasma treated for surface oxidation (iii) plasma treated for water-resistance.

Figure 4: O1s photoelectron peaks: from untreated and HNO₃ treated surfaces.

The treatments performed in the plasma (methods a and b) produced strongly bonded coatings that could be several nanometers in thickness and their surface states were carefully monitored. Figure 5 shows the C1s photoelectron peak from various graphitic surfaces: untreated, and those that have been coated for hydrophilic and hydrophobic behavior using plasma treatment. The major C1s component from

hydrophobic coating on graphite (method b) has a distinctively higher binding energy (290.2 eV) compared to that of uncoated graphite (284.5 eV). This is because the coated surface consists of CF₂ functional groups having C-F bonds whereas the uncoated graphite has pure C-C bonds. The surface with hydrophilic coating (method a) shows minimal C peak because it is mostly Si and O. The small signal at about 283 eV corresponds to traces of Si-C bonding at the graphite-coating interface.

The above observations are supported by other XPS peaks on the same surfaces shown in Figures 6-8. Figure 6 is the O1s peak from surface oxygen, which is strong on the hydrophilic coating. The uncoated surface has traces of oxygen from adsorbed atmospheric moisture and other contaminants. This is completely absent in surfaces treated with hydrophobic coatings indicating enhanced environmental durability of the latter. Figure 7 is the Si2p peak, present only on the hydrophilic surface and Figure 8 is the F1s peak, present only on the hydrophobic surface. It can be concluded from these observations that the hydrophilic surface (treatment i) contains Si and O only (it is SiO_x where x is very close to 2) and the hydrophobic surface (treatment ii) is almost completely (-CF₂)_n, very similar to PTFE or Teflon.

Figure 5: C1s photoelectron peak from graphitic surface that has been coated for hydrophilic and hydrophobic behavior using plasma treatment.

Figure 6: O1s photoelectron peaks. Uncoated graphitic surface has slight contamination, hydrophilic surface has strong component from surface film, and hydrophobic surface has none

Figure 7: Si2p photoelectron peak. Present only on hydrophilic surface.

Figure 8: F1s photoelectron peak. Present only on hydrophobic surface.

In a micro-porous surface such as foam, an estimate of surface affinity for epoxy or other polar compounds can be made from the amount of the water adsorbed in a given time. The amounts of water absorbed by untreated and differently treated foam samples were compared. Results shown in Table 1 indicate that foam treated with nitric acid absorbs more water compared to untreated foam. This supports the hypothesis that increased surface oxygen caused by nitric acid enhances wettability. More significant changes in water absorbability are observed in the plasma treated foams. Compared to untreated foam, nitric acid treated foam has a 61% higher water uptake, and HMDSO-plasma treated foam has a 129% higher water infiltration in 20 minutes. The hydrophobic treatment on the other hand reduces water uptake significantly to about an order of magnitude lower than that of untreated foam.

TABLE I
WEIGHT INCREASE OF FOAM AFTER IMMERSION IN DISTILLED WATER

Time (minutes)	Weight Increase of foam after soaking in water for given time (%)			
	Untreated Foam	Foam treated with HMDSO plasma (Treatment 1)	Foam treated with C3F4 plasma (Treatment 2)	Acid Treated Foam (Treatment 3)
5	32.3	97.5	3.0	64.4
10	33.0	100.1	3.6	68.8
15	34.5	102.6	5.0	74.6
20	47.7	109.1	5.3	76.9

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In summary, several methods of surface modification of micro-cellular graphitic foam have been investigated. The effects of surface activating and surface passivating plasma treatments, as well as that of an oxidizing acid (nitric acid) have been studied using various techniques. It is seen that concentrated nitric acid causes an increase in oxygen-containing groups on the surface, whereas plasma treatments give rise to strongly adherent nano-coatings with distinct functional groups. Treatment with HMDSO plasma creates a surface coating very similar to silica that causes significant increase in infiltration of polar fluids such as water. Treatment with fluorocarbon plasma coats the surface with tetra-fluoro-ethylene (Teflon) that causes drastic reduction of polar fluid infiltration. Future studies on service performance of stand alone foams and of epoxy-infiltrated foam composites foam will help determine the industrial impact of these findings.

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